

QUALITY VERIFICATION BY THE USER

A short questionnaire is available allowing the user to make a preliminary verification about the quality of furniture after a period of use.

Questions are organized keeping into account the safety requirements in compliance with international technical standards and considering the main issues regarding furniture after utilization.

TECHNICAL REFERENCES

- UNI EN 12520:2016 - Furniture - Strength, durability and safety - Requirements for domestic seating. Par. 5.1 General requirements and par. 5.2 Shear and squeeze points.
- UNI EN 14749:2016 - Furniture - Domestic and kitchen storage units and kitchen - worktops - Safety requirements and test methods. Par. 5.2 General safety requirements.
- UNI EN 12521:2015 - Furniture - Strength, durability and safety - Requirements for domestic tables. Par. 5.1 General requirements and par. 5.2 Shear and squeeze points.
- UNI EN 1725:2000 – Domestic Furniture – Beds and mattresses – Safety requirements and test methods

QUESTIONNAIRE

Please indicate yes or no in relation to each characteristic of the furniture to be verified

		YES	NO
1	The furniture maintain its functionality unaltered		
2	The furniture maintain its stability		
3	Presence of deformations		
4	The furniture maintain its aesthetic aspect unaltered		
5	The furniture maintain its cleanability unaltered		
6	All edges are accessible during use are free of burrs and / or sharp edges		
7	Ends of hollow components are closed or capped		
8	Presence of loose load bearing part		
9	End user injuries exclusively caused by the furniture have occurred		
10	Presence of damages		
11	Detachment of the edges		